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Greenwich Meridian in New York? Basque Literary Field in World Literature

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Keywords:	Basque Literature; World Literature; Comparative Literature; Pascale Casanova; Literary Field.
Abstract:	<p>In this paper I analyse the place of the Basque Literary Field in World Literature. Based on a systemic approach of the literature, I propose a dichotomy between Pascale Casanova's theory, where Paris has the centrality of World Literature, and Serge Guilbaut's ideas, where New York is the world's art capital. Thus, I research the historical dynamics of the BLF and, in particular, its link with different literary capitals: Paris, San Sebastian, Madrid and New York. New York, as the global capital of the cultural world, has been exerting more and more influence on the BLF, both on the new generation of writers (Cano, Uribe) and on some writers of the older generation –especially on Atxaga, the most international one–. I finish the paper by postulating that this tendency of the BLF, as an emergent Literary Field, may be interpreted as a global dynamic of World Literature.</p>
Order of Authors:	Beñat Sarasola
Response to Reviewers:	<p>Reviewer #1: Thanks for the comments. Almost all the suggestions have been included (see the file). -Some digressions have been omitted. -As the reviewer states, the article's conceptual framework is based on Casanova (and, Bordieu) and it is not my intention to underestimate her value. Indeed, the only controversy lies on the problem of the WLF's capital. I have included some references (Damrosch) to reinforce the conceptual framework. -A endnote has been included proposing two illustrative examples of the same movement described in the article but outside Basque literature: Gonzalo Torné and Zadie Smith. -New information has been incorporated in order to explain well Uribe's case. -The concep of influence has been explained in an endnote in order to clarify it. One of the article's idea is that the tendency of Basque writers and institutions to court US endorsement is one of the elements that support one of the main thesis: NYC's gain of influence as WLF's capital. -The article had been revised by a native English translator before submitting.</p> <p>Reviewer #2: Thanks for the comments. -The theoretical framework has been reinforced with some new references that are canonical within the field (Damrosh). -The article deals with some of the main Basque contemporary writers: Atxaga, Uribe, Cano. Of course, the majority of Basque writers do not seek NYC's endorsement, but it is significative that precisely the most international Basque writers do seek it. Moreover, it is specially significant that two of them (Uribe, Cano) are part of a new generation.</p>

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7 **Greenwich Meridian in New York? Basque Literary Field in World Literature**

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9 **Beñat Sarasola**

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12 **-University of the Basque Country-**

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22 **Abstract**

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24 In this paper I analyse the place of the Basque Literary Field in World Literature. Based on
25 a systemic approach of the literature, I propose a dichotomy between Pascale Casanova's
26 theory, where Paris has the centrality of World Literature, and Serge Guilbaut's ideas,
27 where New York is the world's art capital. Thus, I research the historical dynamics of the
28 BLF and, in particular, its link with different literary capitals: Paris, San Sebastian, Madrid
29 and New York. New York, as the global capital of the cultural world, has been exerting
30 more and more influence on the BLF, both on the new generation of writers (Cano, Uribe)
31 and on some writers of the older generation –especially on Atxaga, the most international
32 one–. I finish the paper by postulating that this tendency of the BLF, as an emergent
33 Literary Field, may be interpreted as a global dynamic of World Literature.

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44 **Key words:** Basque Literature, World Literature, Comparative Literature, Pascale
45 Casanova, Literary Field.

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1. The Field of Basque Literature

Following systemic theories in the literature, we can say that the Basque Literary Fieldⁱ is a small, dominated space in the World Literary Fieldⁱⁱ, or, using Casanova's terminology, in the World Republic of Letters. Certainly, the main reason for this is the weakness of Basque literature itself and its scanty history. We cannot find any Basque written document until Bernat Etxepare's *Lingua Vasconum Primitiae* in 1545, and, according to researchers (Olaziregi, Kortazar), the Basque literary system was not established until around the 1970s, when the autonomous political institutions in the Peninsular Basque Country were established and the new "(literary) autonomous generation" (Apalategi, 1998) became central.

Therefore, we cannot find a semi-autonomousⁱⁱⁱ BLF until the last decades of 20th century, that is to say, more than a century after the emergence of the French literary field, the first established autonomous literary field (Bordieu).

The lack of influence^{iv} and the weakness of the BLF in the WLF has several important consequences that are not present in the dominant literary fields like those of English, French or Spanish, which are, incidentally, the fields that are on the borders of the BLF^v. That is why the capitals of these literary fields have significantly influenced the BLF, to the point where we could ask whether they have in fact dominated it. The BLF's case is particular in the sense that it has been dealing with three of the most important literary capitals, Paris, Madrid, and, more recently, as we will see, New York.

When taking the history of Basque literature and the origin of the main writers into consideration, one might think that the capital of the BLF should be San Sebastian, Bilbao or Bayonne. Indeed, San Sebastian is probably the current literary capital inside the Basque Country's borders: many of the main writers are from there (Ramon Saizarbitoria, Arantxa

Commented [UdMO1]: Endnote added in order to clarify the concept "influence"

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7 Urretabizkaia) or from the province of Gipuzkoa (Bernardo Atxaga, Anjel Lertxundi,
8 Koldo Izagirre, Harkaitz Cano), the main publishing houses are located there or in the area
9 (Elkar, Erein, Susa, Alberdania), and so are the main journals/newspapers (*Egan, Hegats,*
10 *Jakin, Berria, Argia, Gara*). Nonetheless, if we delve further into the topic, we can also see
11 that the BLF is, to a great extent, a subordinate field and, consequently, the main
12 influential literary capital is located beyond the Basque Country's borders. This movement
13 is what we are going to examine in this paper.
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20 The link between the BLF and the WLF, specifically, between the BLF's internal capital
21 and other capitals abroad brings us to a paradox due to the fact that the reinforcement and
22 the internationalization of Basque literature, through Bernardo Atxaga^{vi}, is directly related
23 to the subordination of the BLF, particularly to the Spanish Literary Field^{vii}. That is why
24 we can link the establishing of the BLF with its subordination.
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31 32 33 **2.Casanova or Guilbaut?**

34 Among the systemic theories of literature, the publication of Pascale Casanova's *La*
35 *République mondiale des Lettres* (The World Republic of Letters) in 1999 was a
36 significant event. The book, inspired in particular by Pierre Bordieu's theories, tried to
37 analyse the dynamics of the world literary system as a whole. She characterized a large
38 Field of World Literature where one could distinguish dominant, dominated and
39 intermediate literature spaces. In fact, she represented the WLF as a *continuum* (2001, 83)
40 between those different literary forces. The distance between the centre of the WLF and a
41 certain space is measurable, according to her, thanks to the "Greenwich meridian of
42 literature" (88), which would be the centre of all centres, the place for modernity and
43 endorsement. Casanova positioned the French Literary Field on this meridian as the most
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7 ancient and, therefore, the most autonomous and influential field in The World Republic of
8 Letters. So, according to Casanova, the FLF (and Paris) is the centre of the WLF.
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13 World literary space is now organized in terms of opposition between, on the one
14 hand, an autonomous pole composed of those spaces that are most endowed in
15 literary resources, which serves as a model and a recourse for writers claiming a
16 position of independence in newly formed spaces (with the result that Paris
17 emerged as a “denationalized” universal capital and a specific measure of literary
18 time was established); and, on the other, a heteronomous pole composed of
19 relatively deprived literary spaces at early stages of development that are
20 dependent on political –typically national– authorities. (108)
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29 Casanova defines Paris as the “central bank of literature” that “is able to create literary
30 value and extend terms of credit everywhere in the world” (127). That is why many of the
31 most important writers of the 20th century who went to Paris obtained this credit. Casanova
32 gives some examples: Samuel Beckett, James Joyce, Danilo Kis, Vladimir Nabokov,
33 William Burroughs, William Faulkner, John Dos Passos, Mario Vargas Llosa... According
34 to her, all these writers were endorsed thanks to Paris, although some were ignored,
35 rejected or even repudiated in their country of origin.
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43 Nevertheless, Casanova is aware also that the WLF was transformed throughout the 20th
44 century and that Paris is no longer the indisputable centre of the WLF. Paris has new
45 capitals competing to be the centre of the WLF –London and New York, especially –,
46 although for her, it has not been substituted yet.
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51 New York and London cannot be said to have replaced Paris in the structure of
52 literary power: one can only note that, as a result of the generalization of the
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7 Anglo-American model and the growing influence of financial considerations,
8 these two capitals tend to acquire more and more power in the literary world.
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13 For Casanova, the main literary conflict in the WLF right now is not about the literary
14 centre, but about the autonomous pole versus the commercial pole.

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17 What is being played out today in every part of the world literary space is not a
18 rivalry between France and the United States or Great Britain but rather a struggle
19 between the commercial pole, which in each country seeks to impose itself as a
20 new source of literary legitimacy through the diffusion of writing that mimics the
21 style of the modern novel, and the autonomous pole, which finds itself under siege
22 not only in the United States and France but throughout Europe, owing to the
23 power of the international publishing giants. (169)

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26 From a very bordieurian perspective, for Casanova the main issue in the WLF throughout
27 the 21st century is to try to preserve the autonomy of the field. Capitalism has obtained
28 such a hegemony and complexity that the risk for the loss of autonomy of the WLF is
29 bigger than ever. But the question about the centrality of the WLF is still open. Casanova
30 appears to suggest that nowadays it is not possible to define a centre as a single capital
31 such as the case of Paris throughout the 19th century. She is reticent about acknowledging
32 any centrality of London or New York (even Brussels) –at least the centrality of the WLF–,
33 and draws a sort of multi-centred WLF. Precisely, the literary capitals that BLF has to deal
34 with (Madrid, Paris and New York) are some of the most important centres in Casanova's
35 framework.

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38 In 1983 Serge Guilbaut wrote a book which has become a reference in the study of art
39 called *How New York Stole the Idea of Modern Art*, where he tried to explain the process

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7 of New York to turn itself into the capital of the art world. This process was, according to
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9 Guilbaut, not only aesthetic but also socio-political. A new artistic avant-garde was created
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11 in the United States, abstract expressionism, with its artistic group (New York School),
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13 major artists (Jackson Pollock, Barnett Newman, Mark Rothko), major critics (Clement
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15 Greenberg, Harold Rosenberg) and major museums (MoMa), and supported by a sort of a
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17 supposed apolitical ideology. In socio-political terms, Guilbaut linked this new artistic
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19 hegemony to the end of the Second World War and the beginning of the Cold War, during
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21 which the United States government used abstract expressionism as a cultural weapon to
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23 display its symbolic cultural power.

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25 If Guilbaut is right, the capital of the World Artistic Field passed in the 1950s from Paris to
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27 New York, and we can say that this status has not changed since then. What we can
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29 examine by extending Guilbaut's theory is whether a similar process has taken place in the
30
31 WLF. Regarding the interconnections within the different fields in the World Cultural
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33 Field, it may not be inappropriate to ask whether something comparable to the WAF
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35 occurred in the WLF. In fact, one of the key references in this debate, Bordieu's *The Rules*
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37 *of Art*, speaks in fundamental terms about the literary field, although as the title suggests,
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39 his theory might be applicable to the art system as a whole. Likewise, Guilbaut's theory,
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41 which deals with the art world, could also be useful in the analysis of the field of literature.

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43 One of the best ways to see which could be the capital of the WLF is to think about the
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45 relations between the main field of literature and other (semi)dominated fields such as
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47 Basque's, that is, the distance between a certain field and the Greenwich Meridian. If we
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49 analyse the way peripheral fields in the WLF relate to this meridian, we can determine
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51 where the most powerful endorsements which are the literary forces of the Greenwich
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53 meridian, can be situated. The relation between periphery and centre is not purely
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55 symbolic, it is determined by other characteristics, such as geography, language or history.

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7 For example, it is common that a field that is situated in a postcolonial context tends to
8 connect with the field where the ancient metropolis was set. For instance, in the Field of
9 Angolan Literature, Lisbon and Portugal have much more power than any other foreign
10 capital because of obvious historical and linguistic reasons. So, an eventual WLF capital
11 cannot be established only by a single analysis of just one peripheral field, but it can give
12 us some interesting clues to understand the dynamic of the WLF more precisely. In fact, as
13 David Damrosch has stated, the establishment of the world literature is a “two-way
14 process” (2003, 27) between world literary capitals and periphery. In this sense, it is
15 especially interesting to make an historical analysis of those symbolic power relations in
16 order to examine the fluctuations of the dominant fields. That is what we aim to do in the
17 following pages with respect to the BLF.
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31 **3. The BLF's capitals:**

32 Even though the BLF was not established until the end of the 20th century, we can identify
33 some previous attempts to set up an autonomous literary field. As Bordieu pointed out,
34 literary autonomy is a fundamental element in establishing a literary field. Hence, we are
35 going to track the moments when literary autonomy took centre stage in the Basque literary
36 debates and in the different capitals that have subsequently influenced the setting up of the
37 BLF.
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47 *3.1 Igela and Paris*

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49 Throughout the Franco dictatorship the Basque culture and literature were almost
50 eliminated. The majority of the publications and the literary activity in this period were
51 located, as a result, in exile^{viii}, in Latin America and France, especially. Many of the most
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7 important figures of the era (Orixe, Andima Ibiñagabeitia, Martin Ugalde, Jokin Zaitegi)
8 settled in Guatemala and Venezuela and published there. Meanwhile, in Paris, Txomin
9 Peillen and Jon Mirande created a highly influential literary journal, *Igela*, in 1963. The
10 journal caused considerable controversy because of its anti-Catholic, critical and satirical
11 character. Indeed, it defined itself as a “heterodox journal”. For example, Mirande's famous
12 poem *Euskaldun zintzoen balada (The Ballad of Good Basques)*, in which he vehemently
13 criticized Basque hegemonic nationalism and Catholicism (embodied by the Basque
14 Nationalist Party, EAJ/PNV), was published in the fourth issue of the journal.
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22 The truth is that Mirande – now a canonical writer in the history of Basque literature –, was
23 not endorsed as such in Paris; however, this is almost the only time when Paris appears as a
24 significant place in Basque literature^x. Written in Basque, *Igela* did not have any weight in
25 the FLF, and its readers were basically located in the Basque Country and in exile in Latin
26 America^x. We should not forget, either, that the BLF had not yet been constituted in the
27 terms specified above, and consequently, we cannot regard Paris as a capital in Basque
28 literature. We can only mention it as an antecedent of an important foreign capital in the
29 history of Basque literature.
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41 3.2 Madrid

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43 The establishment of the BLF in the 1970s is directly related, as we have mentioned, to the
44 development of the autonomous Basque political institutions. The Euskal Autonomi
45 Erkidegoa (Basque Autonomous Community) and the Nafarroako Foru Erkidegoa
46 (Chartered Community of Navarre) were set up in 1979 and 1982, respectively, and most
47 of the institutions that supported the BLF (primary and secondary education, university,
48 culture and language policies, etc.) were established as well at that time. This institutional
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7 set-up, however, is dependent on the Spanish State. So, politically, considering that the
8 Basque Country does not have an independent state, the BLF is, in the end dependent on
9 Madrid too. It is true that a part of the Basque Country is located under the French State,
10 but this part does not have any autonomous institutional set-up, and the Basque cultural
11 and literary situation there is much more dominated. Paradoxically, as the BLF is linked to
12 Madrid's dependent institutions, its (semi)autonomous status is determined by this
13 situation: the BLF "needs" Madrid in order to maintain its autonomy, but at the same time,
14 Madrid is the capital that dominates it. This contradiction can be seen clearly by analysing
15 Bernardo Atxaga's case, which Apalategi has examined in several works.
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24 Atxaga revolutionized the BLF from the end of the 1980s onwards. His book *Obabakoak*
25 won the Spanish National Award for Fiction (Premio Nacional de Narrativa) in 1989 and
26 rapidly endorsed him outside the Basque Country. Firstly in Spain, but soon, mainly thanks
27 to the numerous translations, in many other countries. By 2011, the book had been
28 translated into 25 languages and had won several international awards^{xi}. The book even
29 appeared in the *New York Times Book Review* in 1993, where the critic Eugenio Suárez-
30 Galbán praised *Obabakoak's* literary quality.
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38 All these facts made the definitive professionalization of Atxaga as a writer possible and
39 turned him into the best-known Basque writer. The success introduced Atxaga mainly to
40 the SLF, turning him into one of the most important contemporary Spanish writers.
41 According to Apalategi, Atxaga's position embodied a sociological contradiction due to the
42 fact that the BLF is opposed to the SLF (1999, 66).
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49 Symbolically, this period reaffirmed the era in which Madrid, which had long been the
50 capital of the SLF, became the most influential capital in the BLF. It is significant that
51 sales of *Obabakoak* rose considerably in the Basque Country just after receiving the
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7 National Award, which provides clear proof of the BLF's dependence on the SLP. As a
8 result, Atxaga emerged in the 1990s as the most important writer within the Basque
9 Country's borders, also superseding other important writers such as Txillardegi and
10 Saizarbitoria.
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14 Saizarbitoria's novel *Hamaika pauso* was shortlisted for the Spanish National Award for
15 Fiction in 1996 but did not win the prize in the end. Some years later, when speaking about
16 one of the most important annual events in Basque literature, the Durango Fair, where the
17 publishers present their most important new books, Saizarbitoria complained that there is
18 insufficient time to translate the books properly so they can be entered for the National
19 Award (Etxeberria, 2002, 122). This statement can give us an appropriate measure of the
20 symbolic importance of this award in the BLF. Throughout the 1990s and in the early
21 2000s, the Spanish National Award for Fiction emerged as the most desired award to get
22 definitive endorsement in the BLF and even in the SLF. This idea was reinforced when two
23 other Basque writers, Unai Elorriaga and Kirmen Uribe, won the Spanish National Award
24 for Fiction again in 2002 with *SPrako tranbia (A tram to SP)* and in 2008 with *Bilbao-New*
25 *York-Bilbao*, respectively.
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41 3.3 New York?

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43 Hence, due to geographical, political and historical reasons, we could say that Madrid and
44 the SLF are still the most influential foreign literary space for the BLF. However, there are
45 some signs that indicate that the dominance of the SLF over the BLF is going through a
46 crisis. This gradual change is going to be explored in this part.
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7 3..3.1 *Spanish crisis*

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9 The global financial crisis that erupted in 2007-2008 had particularly far-reaching
10 consequences in Spain. The crisis led to the bursting of a huge real state bubble, which in
11 turn led to a deep recession. The social situation in Spain became very critical; the
12 unemployment rate rose to 25.77% in 2012, with youth unemployment topping 50%. In
13 this context, the social and political unrest increased rapidly, as demonstrated the 15M
14 movement and, afterwards, by the new political party Podemos. Culturally as well, the
15 government was facing growing discontent, especially when taxes on cultural goods were
16 increased significantly in 2012.

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18 Together with the economic crisis, a national crisis linked to Catalonia's pro-independence
19 movement also erupted in Spain. Particularly since 2006, when the Spanish Constitutional
20 Court declared part of the new Statute of Catalonia null and void, the Catalan movement
21 for independence surged.

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23 In this context, we might say that the so-called *Marca España* (Spain Brand)^{xii} value
24 dropped, as did Spain's symbolic power in general.

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38 3..3.2 *Delegitimization of the Spanish National Award for Fiction*

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40 An symptom of this delegitimization of Spanish symbolic power in the cultural field is the
41 number of National Awards that have been turned down in the past few years. Santiago
42 Serra (in Plastic Arts) turned it down in 2010, Javier Marías (in Fiction) in 2012, and
43 Colita (in Photography) and Jordi Savall (in Music) in 2014^{xiii}, all of them for different
44 reasons.

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46 In this sense, it is important to note that misgivings about the award had been raised in the
47 past in the BLF. Two years before *Obabakoak* won the award, Joxe Austin Arrieta's

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7 *Bertso-paper printzatuak* (*Sliced verses*) book of poems was a runner-up in the Spanish
8 National Award for Poetry in 1987, but Arrieta refused to take part for political reasons.

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11 The second Spanish National Award for a Basque writer, Unai Elorriaga's *SPrako tranbia*,
12 also reinforced the delegitimization of the Spanish National Award for Fiction within the
13 BLF. *SPrako tranbia* did not receive the almost unanimous praise that *Obabakoak* got and
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16 it was not regarded as one of the top novels in the history of Basque fiction. In fact, it
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18 failed to get the Euskadi Literatura Saria^{xiv} (Basque Literary Award) –the most important
19 Basque literary award–, or any other leading award. Neither was it translated into English
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21 or French, the dominating literary languages *par excellence*. So, *SPrako tranbia* did not
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23 signify the revolution that *Obabakoak* was responsible for in the BLF –even less so in the
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25 SLF– but the truth is that *Obabakoak* was a unique case, also in the SLF, as explained by
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27 Gabilondo (2006, 157-179). The subsequent novels of Elorriaga, *Van't Hoffen ilea* (2003),
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29 *Vredaman* (2005), *Londres kartoizkoa da* (2009) did not get any special recognition,
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31 either^{xv} and Elorriaga's rating in the BLF gradually declined. His latest novel published in
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33 2005 by a different publishing house (Susa), *Iazko hezurak* (*Last Year's Bones*) did not
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35 receive any special recognition^{xvi}.

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38 This tendency to call into question the Spanish National Award for Fiction increased seven
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40 years later, in 2009, when Kirmen Uribe won it with *Bilbao-New York-Bilbao*. The book
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42 did not get very good reviews in the BLF despite being awarded the Spanish Critics'
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44 Award before winning this award. It was this book that sparked within the BLF open
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46 criticism and delegitimization of the Spanish National Award. There were many critical
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48 reviews expressing the low literary value (Erro/Zaldua, Sarasola) of the book or the
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50 subordinate image of the Basque Country given in it (Retolaza). These criticisms have
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52 been developed in the article *Kanonaren gaineko nazioaz* (*The Nation over the Canon*) by
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54 Ibai Atutxa.

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7 Meanwhile, the criticism of the Spanish National Award as a whole gradually became
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9 widespread within the BLF. As we have seen, the articles written by Apalategi in the 1990s
10 (1998, 1999) and his thesis (2000) exposed the contradictions in Atxaga's case, since he is
11 a dual writer: a Basque and a Spanish writer. Linked to this, Apalategi suggested that the
12 BLF's literary endorsements were too weak compared with the SLF's endorsements, and
13 therefore, the latter prevails over the first. The writer Edorta Jimenez made some
14 controversial statements in 2010 on public Basque television, just after Uribe had won the
15 Spanish National Award, questioning some of the most important Basque critics (Jon
16 Kortazar and Mari Jose Olaziregi) and asking a direct question: "Why does Madrid decide
17 what the Basques have to read?" In another recent book, Ibon Egaña (2015) analysed
18 Basque literary criticism, and concluded that it has a very low legitimating power
19 compared to Spanish literary endorsements. Echoing Apalategi, Egaña says that "the fact
20 that the supreme legitimating power [The Spanish National Award for Fiction] in the BLF
21 is away from it, leads to the proliferation and weakness of the Basque endorsements"
22 (365). The writer Jon Alonso echoed this while presenting his latest book *Hiri hondakin*
23 *solidoak* (Solid urban waste): "We are part of a subordinate literature because the label for
24 the value of true literature isn't granted in our literature, but abroad" (Perez, 2015).
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39 Thus, the tendency to cast doubt on the SLF's influence in the BLF has notably increased
40 in the new century, and it is almost commonplace already among Basque critics and
41 writers.
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48 3.3.3 Seeking New York

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50 In this context, we can see a parallel tendency not so much to reinforce the BLF's literary
51 endorsements but to find another centre abroad that is not Madrid. The delegitimization of
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7 Madrid led to a need to find another more cosmopolitan centre that could surpass Madrid's
8 influence and power. New York, as a hypothetical artistic and literary centre of the world,
9 naturally emerged as the main candidate to replace Madrid^{xvii}.

Commented [UdMO7]: Added in order to extent the idea beyond BLF

13 Throughout the last decade, there have been several attempts to find other ways of
14 translating the works of Basque literature. The usual way to translate these works has been
15 via Spanish, and via Spanish publishing houses. We can see again the dependency of the
16 BLF on the SLF in the tendency to translate Basque books into other languages almost
17 always via a bridge-language (Spanish). This is why Apalategi regarded Atxaga as a
18 Spanish writer as well, because he translated (and adapted) his own works into Spanish,
19 and these second versions were the bridge to other languages and fields of literature.
20 According to Euskal Literatura Itzuliaren Katalogoa (The Catalogue of Translated Basque
21 Literature), 654 works have been translated into Spanish, and only 104 into English (and
22 many of them translated via Spanish). This can give us an indication of the hegemony of
23 the Spanish translations in the BLF. Nevertheless, thanks to the critics that warned of the
24 problems resulting from this dependency, there have been some projects that aimed to open
25 up new ways of translating Basque literature. In this sense, we can cite the books translated
26 into German by the Pahl-Rugenstein Verlag since 2007^{xviii}, or those translated into Dutch
27 by Zirimiri Press^{xix}.

31 Regarding the English translations, it must be said that there have not been any solid
32 publishing projects, either British or American. The only exception is The University of
33 Nevada Press that has published eight books into English, half of them in the last 6 years.
34 However, we have to say that these publications have been produced with the support of
35 the Center for Basque Studies of the University of Nevada, an institution that is entirely
36 engaged to Basque issues. That is to say that there is no commercial publishing line yet in
37 Anglo-Saxon literary fields, with the exception of the translations^{xx} of Atxaga's works. The

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7 works of Basque literature published in New York have been: Atxaga's *Obabakoak*
8 (Pantheon Books, 1992), Laura Mintegi's *Nerea and I^{xxi}* (Peter Lang Press, 2005), Kirmen
9 Uribe's *Meanwhile, Take my hand* (Graywolf Press, 2006) and Unai Elorriaga's *Plants*
10 *don't drink coffee* (Archipelago Books, 2008). So, we cannot speak definitively about an
11 industry of Basque translations in NYC, but we can see a growing trend in translating into
12 English and publishing more there. The best example of that is *Meanwhile, Take My Hand*.
13 Translated by Elizabeth Macklin, the book was published by a prestigious publishing
14 house and was a runner-up in the PEN Award for Poetry in Translation in 2007. Thanks to
15 that, Uribe was able to build up his relations with New York's literary circles. In fact, his
16 following book was the novel *Bilbao-New York-Bilbao*, a book in which, as we will see,
17 NYC has a significant presence, also as an endorsement. In 2018, he obtained the Cullman
18 Center fellowship by The New York Public Library and he lives there since then.

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32 The thing is that in the new literary Basque generation and in its works, NYC exerts an
33 unprecedented weight. It is a utopian imagotype (Sarasola, 2016). Harkaitz Cano and
34 Kirmen Uribe are the two most successful writers of this generation, and both have an
35 intense personal and literary link to NYC. While Cano's NYC is an underground, arty one,
36 Uribe displays a high level, New York literary field, the best example being the passage in
37 *Bilbao-New York-Bilbao^{xxii}* when Uribe is invited to dinner at José Fernández de Albornoz
38 and Scott Hightower's house in Greenwich Village. The other guests are writers, poets or
39 filmmakers, and the house is described as an almost luxury one. Moreover, Uribe gives
40 several readings in different places in Manhattan (at the Bowery Poetry Club, for
41 example), and describes some visits to museums (Frick Collection, MoMa) as well. All
42 these descriptions give us an arty representation of NYC, a utopian imagotype. This
43 tendency of the new generation to look to NYC has not yet produced a consolidated project
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7 to publish and promote these writers there, but at least, the wish of these writers to clear a
8 path to NYC stands out. The literary symbolic power of NYC as a endorsement is evident
9 in these writers.
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13 But this is not only the case of the new generation. In 2011, the Etxepare Basque
14 Institute^{xxiii} created the Bernardo Atxaga Chair at the City University of New York
15 (CUNY). The aim of this chair is “to promote research into and the study of the Basque
16 language and literature” (Etxepare, 2015). The chair offers a doctorate course each year in
17 the Ph.D. Program in Hispanic and Luso-Brazilian Literatures and Languages, where
18 Atxaga himself was the professor in 2015. Firstly, it is important that the only foreign chair
19 for Basque literature is located in NYC, and moreover, that Bernardo Atxaga was the
20 writer chosen. Atxaga is undoubtedly the best-known Basque writer and the only one that
21 could successfully transcend the Iberian field. Besides, he was the first Basque writer to get
22 the Spanish National Award and open his way out of the BLF. Though, in a way, this
23 attempt to promote Atxaga in NYC also shows the limits of the SLF for the BLF and the
24 crisis of the Spanish National Award as a legitimating literary institution. Obtaining this
25 award does not seem important in order to promote a writer abroad beyond the SLF. Just
26 after getting the Mondello prize for *Soinujolearen semea* (*The Accordionist's son*) in 2008,
27 Atxaga publicly complained that he was not given any institutional support, which he felt
28 was essential if writers were to stand any chance of receiving the Nobel Prize in Literature.
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43 The Mexican authorities started promoting Octavio Paz fifteen years before he got
44 the prize; in Portugal many groups also worked for Jose Saramago; the Dutch
45 administration has had a permanent group working for Harry Mulisch in all the
46 trade fairs for years. (...) I lack this third element. (Zabala, 2008)
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7 So, the Bernardo Atxaga Chair, set up three years after this complaint, can be seen as an
8 attempt by the authorities^{xxiv} to cover the shortfall. Since the Nobel Prize is the main means
9 of gaining access to World Literature (Casanova, 2005, 74), promoting Atxaga's candidacy
10 might be the easiest way to achieve the universality of Basque literature.
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15 Here, however, there is a contradiction, because, in reality, securing the support of the
16 American Field of Literature does not seem to be the best way to get the Nobel Prize. The
17 last American writer to get the prize was Toni Morrison in 1993. Since then, for more than
18 twenty years, there have been several US candidates (Philip Roth, Thomas Pynchon...) but
19 with no success. On top of that, the tendency of the Nobel Prize jury to ignore US literature
20 was confirmed when a member of the jury, Horace Engdahl, stated the following in 2008.
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27 Of course there is powerful literature in all big cultures, but you can't get away
28 from the fact that Europe still is the centre of the literary world ... not the United
29 States. The US is too isolated, too insular. They don't translate enough and don't
30 really participate in the big dialogue of literature. That ignorance is restraining.
31 (Goldenberg, 2008)
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37 This statement concurs with Casanova's idea that NYC is not the centre of the WLF.
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39 Moreover, some of the writers that has obtained the Nobel Prize has not received any
40 particular attention by English-speaking reader until then. For example, that is the case of
41 2015 Nobel prize in literature Svetlana Alexievich (Bausells, 2015).
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45 But there is as well a broader perspective that can be added to this line of argument that is
46 linked to a general evolution in contemporary art and literature. Following the studies
47 about globalization, we can see that worldwide culture is highly influenced by Anglo-
48 Saxon culture and for that reason NYC has a dominant status in the WLF. This is not a
49 unique feature of the BLF but of all the fields and subfields of literature. Gabilondo (2012,
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7 46) argues that with globalization, the cultural hegemony of the French language has been
8 replaced by the hegemony of the English language, and therefore, the hegemonic literature
9 within global literature is now Anglo-American literature. He does not name a specific
10 capital for the WLF, but following his reasoning, we can postulate two main options:
11 London or New York. These are the historical main centres within Anglo-American
12 literature, although some scholars point out London's influence is decreasing in favour of
13 New York (Brouillette, 2007, 58). Indirectly, though, Gabilondo points out that China has
14 become the centre of worldwide art sales, recently replacing NYC. However, he stresses
15 that this does not mean that China is the actual centre of the WLF: "Still, Chinese
16 literature, cinema and music have failed to make significant inroads into this multipolar
17 power (except the martial-art films of Hong Kong)" (46). So, we can conclude that for
18 Gabilondo, NYC is still the symbolic centre of the WLF, with China threatening this
19 hegemony.

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32 Another issue linked to this is how a literary work attached to a dominated (*dominé*)
33 literature can achieve –in Casanova's terms– *littérisation*, or in other words, what is the
34 dialectics between dominated and dominant literature fields like. Gabilondo gives some
35 clues in relation to Basque literature by criticizing some aspects of Casanova's theory, in
36 particular, her dichotomy between nationalist and modernist literature. Gabilondo (2012,
37 2013) proposes a more complex system in which a so-called nationalist writer
38 (Saizarbitoria, Sarrionandia) can achieve much more literary autonomy than a so-called
39 modernist one (Atxaga, Uribe) who seeks international success and follows global
40 neoliberal rules. In this sense, the image Uribe gives of the NYC (Sarasola, 2016) concurs
41 with this desire for internationalization described by Gabilondo, although the literary critic
42 alludes to this dependency only with respect to Madrid.

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4- Conclusions

The BLF is in a relevant situation when the forces in the WLF are analysed. Situated geographically between France and Spain and, therefore, between two of the most powerful fields of literature, and under the ongoing influence, in the current globalized world, of the Field of Literature of the United States, the BLF is subject to fast power changes. Although the BLF has developed considerably within only a few decades and is now a relatively consistent literary field in southern Europe, Madrid and New York are still the two capitals that are symbolically dominating it. Specially Madrid, as has been already pointed out, among others, by Apalategi, Egaña, Gabilondo. Nevertheless, at the same time, we can see a ongoing tendency to seek legitimization power in New York.

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We can establish three periods in modern Basque literature in which it has been dominated by three different capitals.

Firstly, it was in the 1970s and 1980s that the BLF was instituted as such, in other words, when Basque literature acquired (semi)autonomy and set up an economic and cultural system. This was the era that saw the setting up of the autonomous Basque institutions, the UPV/EHU-University of the Basque Country, the main publishing houses, many literary journals etc. In this context, Donostia-San Sebastian was the main capital of the field, because the most important literary agents were located there or around there.

At the beginning of the 1990s, while the power of the BLF was increasing, another capital, this time a foreign one, appeared as the most influential capital for Basque literature. Symbolically, coinciding with the Spanish National Award that Atxaga's *Obabakoak* received in 1989, Madrid became the capital of the BLF. In order to gain literary recognition, a Basque writer needed to be translated into Spanish (by a Spanish publishing house) and be recognized in Madrid (via awards etc.). Many Basque writers were,

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7 therefore, looking towards Madrid, as Saizarbitoria's complaint about the lack of time to
8 translate in the time between the Durango Fair and the submission deadline for the Spanish
9 National Award shows. This dependency was confirmed in a way in 2002 when
10 Elorriaga's *SPrako tranbia* won the same award, and he, who had not had anything
11 published before, became quickly endorsed with his *opera prima*. Something similar
12 happened with Uribe and *Bilbao-New York-Bilbao*.
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18 Nevertheless, parallel to this process, the symbolic power of Madrid, and of the Spanish
19 National Award, in particular, seemed to be suffering fatigue. Partly due to the context of
20 the social and cultural crisis in Spain and the loss of the legitimization power of the award,
21 some Basque writers have tried to seek endorsement by other means. This is especially
22 clear in the new generations, in Cano and Uribe, the only two professional writers of their
23 generation^{xxv}. Both have shown, each in a different way, an inclination towards New York
24 and have portrayed the city as the place to go for a writer or an artist. New York is for
25 Uribe the place where one can get definitive literary or artistic endorsement, the place to
26 recite your writings (Bowery Poetry Club) and to go to literary events and dinners. This is
27 not, however, unique to the writers of the new generation. Even a writer who has been
28 consecrated internationally via Madrid like Atxaga has become linked to New York
29 recently. The Atxaga Chair at the University of New York can be regarded as the latest
30 major effort of the BLF to get endorsement in New York. All this shows that the SLF is
31 not sufficient in order to get international recognition and enter the World Republic of
32 Letters.
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47 Following this argument, we could ask whether this might be seen as a part of a bigger
48 process in which the power relations in the WLF have changed in the last few decades. The
49 BLF, as a relatively small emergent literary field, can show us some tendencies of these
50 types of fields that point to the capitals where they are seeking endorsement. In this sense,
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it seems appropriate to point out that the BLF has not manifested any interest in Paris in order to get international literary recognition, even when part of the BLF is located in the French State. In that respect it is important to note that some important Basque writers from the Continental Basque Country that are translated into French and/or write as well in French, have been endorsed in the Peninsular Basque Country, that is to say, in the part that is within the Spanish State. All this suggest to us that in a multipolar globalized WLF, Paris is no longer the capital of the World Republic of Letters, and that New York has nowadays a much more power of endorsement.

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15 i
16 i Hereinafter the BLF.

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18 ii Hereinafter the WLF.

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21 iii We prefer to speak about semi-autonomy rather than autonomy following Hal Foster's
22 (2011) characterization of aesthetic autonomy.

23 iv The concept of “influence” used in the article is understood in mere systemic terms, that is radically
24 different from the stylistic meaning more commonly used in literary studies. By the term influence we refer
25 to the legitimization power of a certain literary field and, consequently, it’s power to attract other fields to
26 it’s dynamics and structures.

27 v
28 v In geographical terms, the BLF borders on the French Literary Field to the North and the
29 Spanish Literary Field to the South. Moreover, there is a space in the BLF linked to the English Literary
30 Field, consisting of the literature of the American diaspora, such as Robert Laxalt's works.

31 vi Atxaga has been “thoroughly recognized for having internationalized Basque literature” (González-Allende
32 & Ascunce, 2018). He has received several international literary prizes: Grinzane Cavour, Mondello, Cesare
33 Pavese, Spanish National Prize.

34 vii
35 vii Hereinafter the SLF.

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37 viii Maybe, the most important exception was Koldo Mitxelena and the journal *Egan*.

38 ix
39 ix This is definitely a rarity bearing in mind that a part of the Basque Country (Iparralde or
40 the Continental Basque Country) is located within the French State, and that many important Basque writers
41 come from there. In any case, the issue is that Paris has no influence on the BLF, particularly when compared
42 with Madrid's influence.

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44 x Andima Ibiñagabeitia, for example, one of Mirande's closest friends and the man who
45 introduced Peillen to him, was living in Caracas at that time.

46 xi
47 xi Milles Pages Prize, Atlantic Pyrenees Three Crowns Prize and shortlisted for the European
48 Literary Prize.

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51 xii A State policy formulated in 2012 and which aims to promote Spain abroad.
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- xiii Years before there had been other refusal: Els Joglars company in 1994 (in Theatre), and Daniel Gil in 2001 (in Design)
- xiv *Obabakoak* received it in 1989.
- xv They did not receive any awards at all.
- xvi It received the Spanish Critics' Award, but this award is actually given by only one or two critics (Jon Kortazar and/or Javier Rojo) opinion.
- xvii This tendency could be identified even within SLF, especially in new generations authors that are being endorsed by New York. One of these examples is Gonzalo Torné, a Catalan writer writing in Spanish that can be situated within the North American modernist literary tradition. His work has been translated into English and reviewed and praised in the New York Times. More clearly, Zadie Smith is a good example of an author that the international success is linked to her arrival to New York and the development of her literary career there.
- xviii *Kilkerren hotsak* (Edorta Jimenez), *Koaderno gorria* (Arantxa Urretabizkaia), *Rock'n Roll* (Aingeru Epaltza), *Hamaseigarrenean aidanez* (Anjel Lertxundi), *Pasaia blues* (Harkaitz Cano), *Amaren eskuak* (Karmele Jaio) and *Zulo bat uretan* (Iñigo Aranbarri), all translated directly from Basque.
- xix The short story anthology *Emekiro, Sisifo maiteminez* (Laura Mintegi), *Norbait dabil sute eskailean* (Harkaitz Cano), and *Han goitik itsasoa ikusten da* (Julen Gabiria), all translated directly from Basque.
- xx The main works have been published by Harvill Secker, and translated by Margaret Jull.
- xxi *Nerea eta biok*.
- xxii *Bilbao-New York-Bilbao* is an autofictional novel.
- xxiii The institute whose aim is to promote Basque culture all over the world.
- xxiv The Etxepare Basque Institute is a public institute that reports to the Basque Autonomous Community Government.

Greenwich Meridian in New York? Basque Literary Field in World Literature

-University of the Basque Country-

Abstract

In this paper I analyse the place of the Basque Literary Field in World Literature. Based on a systemic approach of the literature, I propose a dichotomy between Pascale Casanova's theory, where Paris has the centrality of World Literature, and Serge Guilbaut's ideas, where New York is the world's art capital. Thus, I research the historical dynamics of the BLF and, in particular, its link with different literary capitals: Paris, San Sebastian, Madrid and New York. New York, as the global capital of the cultural world, has been exerting more and more influence on the BLF, both on the new generation of writers (Cano, Uribe) and on some writers of the older generation –especially on Atxaga, the most international one–. I finish the paper by postulating that this tendency of the BLF, as an emergent Literary Field, may be interpreted as a global dynamic of World Literature.

Key words: Basque Literature, World Literature, Comparative Literature, Pascale Casanova, Literary Field.

1. The Field of Basque Literature

Following systemic theories in the literature, we can say that the Basque Literary Fieldⁱ is a small, dominated space in the World Literary Fieldⁱⁱ, or, using Casanova's terminology, in the World Republic of Letters. Certainly, the main reason for this is the weakness of Basque literature itself and its scanty history. We cannot find any Basque written document until Bernat Etxepare's *Lingua Vasconum Primitiae* in 1545, and, according to researchers (Olaziregi, Kortazar), the Basque literary system was not established until around the 1970s, when the autonomous political institutions in the Peninsular Basque Country were established and the new "(literary) autonomous generation" (Apalategi, 1998) became central.

Therefore, we cannot find a semi-autonomousⁱⁱⁱ BLF until the last decades of 20th century, that is to say, more than a century after the emergence of the French literary field, the first established autonomous literary field (Bordieu).

The lack of influence^{iv} and the weakness of the BLF in the WLF has several important consequences that are not present in the dominant literary fields like those of English, French or Spanish, which are, incidentally, the fields that are on the borders of the BLF^v. That is why the capitals of these literary fields have significantly influenced the BLF, to the point where we could ask whether they have in fact dominated it. The BLF's case is particular in the sense that it has been dealing with three of the most important literary capitals, Paris, Madrid, and, more recently, as we will see, New York.

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When taking the history of Basque literature and the origin of the main writers into consideration, one might think that the capital of the BLF should be San Sebastian, Bilbao or Bayonne. Indeed, San Sebastian is probably the current literary capital inside the Basque Country's borders: many of the main writers are from there (Ramon Saizarbitoria, Arantxa Urretabizkaia) or from the province of Gipuzkoa (Bernardo Atxaga, Anjel Lertxundi, Koldo

Izagirre, Harkaitz Cano), the main publishing houses are located there or in the area (Elkar, Erein, Susa, Alberdania), and so are the main journals/newspapers (*Egan, Hegats, Jakin, Berria, Argia, Gara*). Nonetheless, if we delve further into the topic, we can also see that the BLF is, to a great extent, a subordinate field and, consequently, the main influential literary capital is located beyond the Basque Country's borders. This movement is what we are going to examine in this paper.

The link between the BLF and the WLF, specifically, between the BLF's internal capital and other capitals abroad brings us to a paradox due to the fact that the reinforcement and the internationalization of Basque literature, through Bernardo Atxaga^{vi}, is directly related to the subordination of the BLF, particularly to the Spanish Literary Field^{vii}. That is why we can link the establishing of the BLF with its subordination.

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2.Casanova or Guilbaut?

Among the systemic theories of literature, the publication of Pascale Casanova's *La République mondiale des Lettres* (The World Republic of Letters) in 1999 was a significant event. The book, inspired in particular by Pierre Bourdieu's theories, tried to analyse the dynamics of the world literary system as a whole. She characterized a large Field of World Literature where one could distinguish dominant, dominated and intermediate literature spaces. In fact, she represented the WLF as a *continuum* (2001, 83) between those different literary forces. The distance between the centre of the WLF and a certain space is measurable, according to her, thanks to the "Greenwich meridian of literature" (88), which would be the centre of all centres, the place for modernity and endorsement. Casanova positioned the French Literary Field on this meridian as the most ancient and, therefore, the

most autonomous and influential field in The World Republic of Letters. So, according to Casanova, the FLF (and Paris) is the centre of the WLF.

World literary space is now organized in terms of opposition between, on the one hand, an autonomous pole composed of those spaces that are most endowed in literary resources, which serves as a model and a recourse for writers claiming a position of independence in newly formed spaces (with the result that Paris emerged as a “denationalized” universal capital and a specific measure of literary time was established); and, on the other, a heteronomous pole composed of relatively deprived literary spaces at early stages of development that are dependent on political –typically national– authorities. (108)

Casanova defines Paris as the “central bank of literature” that “is able to create literary value and extend terms of credit everywhere in the world” (127). That is why many of the most important writers of the 20th century who went to Paris obtained this credit. Casanova gives some examples: Samuel Beckett, James Joyce, Danilo Kis, Vladimir Nabokov, William Burroughs, William Faulkner, John Dos Passos, Mario Vargas Llosa... According to her, all these writers were endorsed thanks to Paris, although some were ignored, rejected or even repudiated in their country of origin.

Nevertheless, Casanova is aware also that the WLF was transformed throughout the 20th century and that Paris is no longer the indisputable centre of the WLF. Paris has new capitals competing to be the centre of the WLF –London and New York, especially –, although for her, it has not been substituted yet.

New York and London cannot be said to have replaced Paris in the structure of literary power: one can only note that, as a result of the generalization of the Anglo-

American model and the growing influence of financial considerations, these two capitals tend to acquire more and more power in the literary world. (168)

For Casanova, the main literary conflict in the WLF right now is not about the literary centre, but about the autonomous pole versus the commercial pole.

What is being played out today in every part of the world literary space is not a rivalry between France and the United States or Great Britain but rather a struggle between the commercial pole, which in each country seeks to impose itself as a new source of literary legitimacy through the diffusion of writing that mimics the style of the modern novel, and the autonomous pole, which finds itself under siege not only in the United States and France but throughout Europe, owing to the power of the international publishing giants. (169)

From a very bordieurian perspective, for Casanova the main issue in the WLF throughout the 21st century is to try to preserve the autonomy of the field. Capitalism has obtained such a hegemony and complexity that the risk for the loss of autonomy of the WLF is bigger than ever. But the question about the centrality of the WLF is still open. Casanova appears to suggest that nowadays it is not possible to define a centre as a single capital such as the case of Paris throughout the 19th century. She is reticent about acknowledging any centrality of London or New York (even Brussels) –at least the centrality of the WLF–, and draws a sort of multi-centred WLF. Precisely, the literary capitals that BLF has to deal with (Madrid, Paris and New York) are some of the most important centres in Casanova’s framework.

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In 1983 Serge Guilbaut wrote a book which has become a reference in the study of art called *How New York Stole the Idea of Modern Art*, where he tried to explain the process of New York to turn itself into the capital of the art world. This process was, according to Guilbaut, not only aesthetic but also socio-political. A new artistic avant-garde was created in the

United States, abstract expressionism, with its artistic group (New York School), major artists (Jackson Pollock, Barnett Newman, Mark Rothko), major critics (Clement Greenberg, Harold Rosenberg) and major museums (MoMa), and supported by a sort of a supposed apolitical ideology. In socio-political terms, Guilbaut linked this new artistic hegemony to the end of the Second World War and the beginning of the Cold War, during which the United States government used abstract expressionism as a cultural weapon to display its symbolic cultural power.

If Guilbaut is right, the capital of the World Artistic Field passed in the 1950s from Paris to New York, and we can say that this status has not changed since then. What we can examine by extending Guilbaut's theory is whether a similar process has taken place in the WLF. Regarding the interconnections within the different fields in the World Cultural Field, it may not be inappropriate to ask whether something comparable to the WAF occurred in the WLF. In fact, one of the key references in this debate, Bordieu's *The Rules of Art*, speaks in fundamental terms about the literary field, although as the title suggests, his theory might be applicable to the art system as a whole. Likewise, Guilbaut's theory, which deals with the art world, could also be useful in the analysis of the field of literature.

One of the best ways to see which could be the capital of the WLF is to think about the relations between the main field of literature and other (semi)dominated fields such as Basque's, that is, the distance between a certain field and the Greenwich Meridian. If we analyse the way peripheral fields in the WLF relate to this meridian, we can determine where the most powerful endorsements which are the literary forces of the Greenwich meridian, can be situated. The relation between periphery and centre is not purely symbolic, it is determined by other characteristics, such as geography, language or history.

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For example, it is common that a field that is situated in a postcolonial context tends to connect with the field where the ancient metropolis was set. For instance, in the Field of Angolan Literature, Lisbon and Portugal have much more power than any other foreign capital because of obvious historical and linguistic reasons. So, an eventual WLF capital cannot be established only by a single analysis of just one peripheral field, but it can give us some interesting clues to understand the dynamic of the WLF more precisely. In fact, as David Damrosch has stated, the establishment of the world literature is a “two-way process” (2003, 27) between world literary capitals and periphery. In this sense, it is especially interesting to make an historical analysis of those symbolic power relations in order to examine the fluctuations of the dominant fields. That is what we aim to do in the following pages with respect to the BLF.

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3. The BLF's capitals:

Even though the BLF was not established until the end of the 20th century, we can identify some previous attempts to set up an autonomous literary field. As Bordieu pointed out, literary autonomy is a fundamental element in establishing a literary field. Hence, we are going to track the moments when literary autonomy took centre stage in the Basque literary debates and in the different capitals that have subsequently influenced the setting up of the BLF.

3.1 *Igela and Paris*

Throughout the Franco dictatorship the Basque culture and literature were almost eliminated. The majority of the publications and the literary activity in this period were located, as a result, in exile^{viii}, in Latin America and France, especially. Many of the most important

figures of the era (Orixe, Andima Ibiñagabeitia, Martin Ugalde, Jokin Zaitegi) settled in Guatemala and Venezuela and published there. Meanwhile, in Paris, Txomin Peillen and Jon Mirande created a highly influential literary journal, *Igela*, in 1963. The journal caused considerable controversy because of its anti-Catholic, critical and satirical character. Indeed, it defined itself as a “heterodox journal”. For example, Mirande's famous poem *Euskaldun zintzoen balada* (*The Ballad of Good Basques*), in which he vehemently criticized Basque hegemonic nationalism and Catholicism (embodied by the Basque Nationalist Party, EAJ/PNV), was published in the fourth issue of the journal.

The truth is that Mirande – now a canonical writer in the history of Basque literature –, was not endorsed as such in Paris; however, this is almost the only time when Paris appears as a significant place in Basque literature^x. Written in Basque, *Igela* did not have any weight in the FLF, and its readers were basically located in the Basque Country and in exile in Latin America^x. We should not forget, either, that the BLF had not yet been constituted in the terms specified above, and consequently, we cannot regard Paris as a capital in Basque literature. We can only mention it as an antecedent of an important foreign capital in the history of Basque literature.

3.2 Madrid

The establishment of the BLF in the 1970s is directly related, as we have mentioned, to the development of the autonomous Basque political institutions. The Euskal Autonomi Erkidegoa (Basque Autonomous Community) and the Nafarroako Foru Erkidegoa (Chartered Community of Navarre) were set up in 1979 and 1982, respectively, and most of the institutions that supported the BLF (primary and secondary education, university, culture and language policies, etc.) were established as well at that time. This institutional set-up,

however, is dependent on the Spanish State. So, politically, considering that the Basque Country does not have an independent state, the BLF is, in the end dependent on Madrid too. It is true that a part of the Basque Country is located under the French State, but this part does not have any autonomous institutional set-up, and the Basque cultural and literary situation there is much more dominated. Paradoxically, as the BLF is linked to Madrid's dependent institutions, its (semi)autonomous status is determined by this situation: the BLF “needs” Madrid in order to maintain its autonomy, but at the same time, Madrid is the capital that dominates it. This contradiction can be seen clearly by analysing Bernardo Atxaga's case, which Apalategi has examined in several works.

Atxaga revolutionized the BLF from the end of the 1980s onwards. His book *Obabakoak* won the Spanish National Award for Fiction (Premio Nacional de Narrativa) in 1989 and rapidly endorsed him outside the Basque Country. Firstly in Spain, but soon, mainly thanks to the numerous translations, in many other countries. By 2011, the book had been translated into 25 languages and had won several international awards^{xi}. The book even appeared in the *New York Times Book Review* in 1993, where the critic Eugenio Suárez-Galbán praised *Obabakoak's* literary quality.

All these facts made the definitive professionalization of Atxaga as a writer possible and turned him into the best-known Basque writer. The success introduced Atxaga mainly to the SLF, turning him into one of the most important contemporary Spanish writers. According to Apalategi, Atxaga's position embodied a sociological contradiction due to the fact that the BLF is opposed to the SLF (1999, 66).

Symbolically, this period reaffirmed the era in which Madrid, which had long been the capital of the SLF, became the most influential capital in the BLF. It is significant that sales of *Obabakoak* rose considerably in the Basque Country just after receiving the National

Award, which provides clear proof of the BLF's dependence on the SLP. As a result, Atxaga emerged in the 1990s as the most important writer within the Basque Country's borders, also superseding other important writers such as Txillardegi and Saizarbitoria.

Saizarbitoria's novel *Hamaika pauso* was shortlisted for the Spanish National Award for Fiction in 1996 but did not win the prize in the end. Some years later, when speaking about one of the most important annual events in Basque literature, the Durango Fair, where the publishers present their most important new books, Saizarbitoria complained that there is insufficient time to translate the books properly so they can be entered for the National Award (Etxeberria, 2002, 122). This statement can give us an appropriate measure of the symbolic importance of this award in the BLF. Throughout the 1990s and in the early 2000s, the Spanish National Award for Fiction emerged as the most desired award to get definitive endorsement in the BLF and even in the SLF. This idea was reinforced when two other Basque writers, Unai Elorriaga and Kirmen Uribe, won the Spanish National Award for Fiction again in 2002 with *SPrako tranbia (A tram to SP)* and in 2008 with *Bilbao-New York-Bilbao*, respectively.

3.3 New York?

Hence, due to geographical, political and historical reasons, we could say that Madrid and the SLF are still the most influential foreign literary space for the BLF. However, there are some signs that indicate that the dominance of the SLF over the BLF is going through a crisis. This gradual change is going to be explored in this part.

3.3.1 Spanish crisis

The global financial crisis that erupted in 2007-2008 had particularly far-reaching consequences in Spain. The crisis led to the bursting of a huge real state bubble, which in turn led to a deep recession. The social situation in Spain became very critical; the unemployment rate rose to 25.77% in 2012, with youth unemployment topping 50%. In this context, the social and political unrest increased rapidly, as demonstrated the 15M movement and, afterwards, by the new political party Podemos. Culturally as well, the government was facing growing discontent, especially when taxes on cultural goods were increased significantly in 2012.

Together with the economic crisis, a national crisis linked to Catalonia's pro-independence movement also erupted in Spain. Particularly since 2006, when the Spanish Constitutional Court declared part of the new Statute of Catalonia null and void, the Catalan movement for independence surged.

In this context, we might say that the so-called *Marca España* (Spain Brand)^{xii} value dropped, as did Spain's symbolic power in general.

3.3.2 *Delegitimization of the Spanish National Award for Fiction*

An symptom of this delegitimization of Spanish symbolic power in the cultural field is the number of National Awards that have been turned down in the past few years. Santiago Serra (in Plastic Arts) turned it down in 2010, Javier Marías (in Fiction) in 2012, and Colita (in Photography) and Jordi Savall (in Music) in 2014^{xiii}, all of them for different reasons.

In this sense, it is important to note that misgivings about the award had been raised in the past in the BLF. Two years before *Obabakoak* won the award, Joxe Austin Arrieta's *Bertso-paper printzatuak* (*Sliced verses*) book of poems was a runner-up in the Spanish National Award for Poetry in 1987, but Arrieta refused to take part for political reasons.

The second Spanish National Award for a Basque writer, Unai Elorriaga's *SPrako tranbia*, also reinforced the delegitimization of the Spanish National Award for Fiction within the BLF. *SPrako tranbia* did not receive the almost unanimous praise that *Obabakoak* got and it was not regarded as one of the top novels in the history of Basque fiction. In fact, it failed to get the Euskadi Literatura Saria^{xiv} (Basque Literary Award) –the most important Basque literary award–, or any other leading award. Neither was it translated into English or French, the dominating literary languages *par excellence*. So, *SPrako tranbia* did not signify the revolution that *Obabakoak* was responsible for in the BLF –even less so in the SLF– but the truth is that *Obabakoak* was a unique case, also in the SLF, as explained by Gabilondo (2006, 157-179). The subsequent novels of Elorriaga, *Van't Hoffen ilea* (2003), *Vredaman* (2005), *Londres kartoizkoa da* (2009) did not get any special recognition, either^{xv} and Elorriaga's rating in the BLF gradually declined. His latest novel published in 2005 by a different publishing house (Susa), *Iazko hezurrak* (*Last Year's Bones*) did not receive any special recognition^{xvi}.

This tendency to call into question the Spanish National Award for Fiction increased seven years later, in 2009, when Kirmen Uribe won it with *Bilbao-New York-Bilbao*. The book did not get very good reviews in the BLF despite being awarded the Spanish Critics' Award before winning this award. It was this book that sparked within the BLF open criticism and delegitimization of the Spanish National Award. There were many critical reviews expressing the low literary value (Erro/Zaldua, Sarasola) of the book or the subordinate image of the Basque Country given in it (Retolaza). These criticisms have been developed in the article *Kanonaren gaineko nazioaz* (*The Nation over the Canon*) by Ibai Atutxa.

Meanwhile, the criticism of the Spanish National Award as a whole gradually became widespread within the BLF. As we have seen, the articles written by Apalategi in the 1990s (1998, 1999) and his thesis (2000) exposed the contradictions in Atxaga's case, since he is a

dual writer: a Basque and a Spanish writer. Linked to this, Apalategi suggested that the BLF's literary endorsements were too weak compared with the SLF's endorsements, and therefore, the latter prevails over the first. The writer Edorta Jimenez made some controversial statements in 2010 on public Basque television, just after Uribe had won the Spanish National Award, questioning some of the most important Basque critics (Jon Kortazar and Mari Jose Olaziregi) and asking a direct question: "Why does Madrid decide what the Basques have to read?" In another recent book, Ibon Egaña (2015) analysed Basque literary criticism, and concluded that it has a very low legitimating power compared to Spanish literary endorsements. Echoing Apalategi, Egaña says that "the fact that the supreme legitimating power [The Spanish National Award for Fiction] in the BLF is away from it, leads to the proliferation and weakness of the Basque endorsements" (365). The writer Jon Alonso echoed this while presenting his latest book *Hiri hondakin solidoak* (Solid urban waste): "We are part of a subordinate literature because the label for the value of true literature isn't granted in our literature, but abroad" (Perez, 2015).

Thus, the tendency to cast doubt on the SLF's influence in the BLF has notably increased in the new century, and it is almost commonplace already among Basque critics and writers.

3.3.3 Seeking New York

In this context, we can see a parallel tendency not so much to reinforce the BLF's literary endorsements but to find another centre abroad that is not Madrid. The delegitimization of Madrid led to a need to find another more cosmopolitan centre that could surpass Madrid's influence and power. New York, as a hypothetical artistic and literary centre of the world, naturally emerged as the main candidate to replace Madrid^{xvii}.

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Throughout the last decade, there have been several attempts to find other ways of translating the works of Basque literature. The usual way to translate these works has been via Spanish, and via Spanish publishing houses. We can see again the dependency of the BLF on the SLF in the tendency to translate Basque books into other languages almost always via a bridge-language (Spanish). This is why Apalategi regarded Atxaga as a Spanish writer as well, because he translated (and adapted) his own works into Spanish, and these second versions were the bridge to other languages and fields of literature. According to Euskal Literatura Itzuliaren Katalogoa (The Catalogue of Translated Basque Literature), 654 works have been translated into Spanish, and only 104 into English (and many of them translated via Spanish). This can give us an indication of the hegemony of the Spanish translations in the BLF. Nevertheless, thanks to the critics that warned of the problems resulting from this dependency, there have been some projects that aimed to open up new ways of translating Basque literature. In this sense, we can cite the books translated into German by the Pahl-Rugenstein Verlag since 2007^{xviii}, or those translated into Dutch by Zirimiri Press^{xix}.

Regarding the English translations, it must be said that there have not been any solid publishing projects, either British or American. The only exception is The University of Nevada Press that has published eight books into English, half of them in the last 6 years. However, we have to say that these publications have been produced with the support of the Center for Basque Studies of the University of Nevada, an institution that is entirely engaged to Basque issues. That is to say that there is no commercial publishing line yet in Anglo-Saxon literary fields, with the exception of the translations^{xx} of Atxaga's works. The works of Basque literature published in New York have been: Atxaga's *Obabakoak* (Pantheon Books, 1992), Laura Mintegi's *Nerea and I*^{xxi} (Peter Lang Press, 2005), Kirmen Uribe's *Meanwhile, Take my hand* (Graywolf Press, 2006) and Unai Elorriaga's *Plants don't drink coffee* (Archipelago Books, 2008). So, we cannot speak definitively about an industry of

Basque translations in NYC, but we can see a growing trend in translating into English and publishing more there. The best example of that is *Meanwhile, Take My Hand*. Translated by Elizabeth Macklin, the book was published by a prestigious publishing house and was a runner-up in the PEN Award for Poetry in Translation in 2007. Thanks to that, Uribe was able to build up his relations with New York's literary circles. In fact, his following book was the novel *Bilbao-New York-Bilbao*, a book in which, as we will see, NYC has a significant presence, also as an endorsement. In 2018, he obtained the Cullman Center fellowship by The New York Public Library and he lives there since then.

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The thing is that in the new literary Basque generation and in its works, NYC exerts an unprecedented weight. It is a utopian imagotype (Sarasola, 2016). Harkaitz Cano and Kirmen Uribe are the two most successful writers of this generation, and both have an intense personal and literary link to NYC. While Cano's NYC is an underground, arty one, Uribe displays a high level, New York literary field, the best example being the passage in *Bilbao-New York-Bilbao*^{xxii} when Uribe is invited to dinner at José Fernández de Albornoz and Scott Hightower's house in Greenwich Village. The other guests are writers, poets or filmmakers, and the house is described as an almost luxury one. Moreover, Uribe gives several readings in different places in Manhattan (at the Bowery Poetry Club, for example), and describes some visits to museums (Frick Collection, MoMa) as well. All these descriptions give us an arty representation of NYC, a utopian imagotype. This tendency of the new generation to look to NYC has not yet produced a consolidated project to publish and promote these writers there, but at least, the wish of these writers to clear a path to NYC stands out. The literary symbolic power of NYC as an endorsement is evident in these writers.

But this is not only the case of the new generation. In 2011, the Etxepare Basque Institute^{xxiii} created the Bernardo Atxaga Chair at the City University of New York (CUNY). The aim of this chair is “to promote research into and the study of the Basque language and literature” (Etxepare, 2015). The chair offers a doctorate course each year in the Ph.D. Program in Hispanic and Luso-Brazilian Literatures and Languages, where Atxaga himself was the professor in 2015. Firstly, it is important that the only foreign chair for Basque literature is located in NYC, and moreover, that Bernardo Atxaga was the writer chosen. Atxaga is undoubtedly the best-known Basque writer and the only one that could successfully transcend the Iberian field. Besides, he was the first Basque writer to get the Spanish National Award and open his way out of the BLF. Though, in a way, this attempt to promote Atxaga in NYC also shows the limits of the SLF for the BLF and the crisis of the Spanish National Award as a legitimating literary institution. Obtaining this award does not seem important in order to promote a writer abroad beyond the SLF. Just after getting the Mondello prize for *Soinujolearen semea* (*The Accordionist's son*) in 2008, Atxaga publicly complained that he was not given any institutional support, which he felt was essential if writers were to stand any chance of receiving the Nobel Prize in Literature.

The Mexican authorities started promoting Octavio Paz fifteen years before he got the prize; in Portugal many groups also worked for Jose Saramago; the Dutch administration has had a permanent group working for Harry Mulisch in all the trade fairs for years. (...) I lack this third element. (Zabala, 2008)

So, the Bernardo Atxaga Chair, set up three years after this complaint, can be seen as an attempt by the authorities^{xxiv} to cover the shortfall. Since the Nobel Prize is the main means of gaining access to World Literature (Casanova, 2005, 74), promoting Atxaga's candidacy might be the easiest way to achieve the universality of Basque literature.

Here, however, there is a contradiction, because, in reality, securing the support of the American Field of Literature does not seem to be the best way to get the Nobel Prize. The last American writer to get the prize was Toni Morrison in 1993. Since then, for more than twenty years, there have been several US candidates (Philip Roth, Thomas Pynchon...) but with no success. On top of that, the tendency of the Nobel Prize jury to ignore US literature was confirmed when a member of the jury, Horace Engdahl, stated the following in 2008.

Of course there is powerful literature in all big cultures, but you can't get away from the fact that Europe still is the centre of the literary world ... not the United States. The US is too isolated, too insular. They don't translate enough and don't really participate in the big dialogue of literature. That ignorance is restraining. (Goldenberg, 2008)

This statement concurs with Casanova's idea that NYC is not the centre of the WLF. Moreover, some of the writers that has obtained the Nobel Prize has not received any particular attention by English-speaking reader until then. For example, that is the case of 2015 Nobel prize in literature Svetlana Alexievich (Bausells, 2015).

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But there is as well a broader perspective that can be added to this line of argument that is linked to a general evolution in contemporary art and literature. Following the studies about globalization, we can see that worldwide culture is highly influenced by Anglo-Saxon culture and for that reason NYC has a dominant status in the WLF. This is not a unique feature of the BLF but of all the fields and subfields of literature. Gabilondo (2012, 46) argues that with globalization, the cultural hegemony of the French language has been replaced by the hegemony of the English language, and therefore, the hegemonic literature within global literature is now Anglo-American literature. He does not name a specific capital for the WLF, but following his reasoning, we can postulate two main options: London

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or New York. These are the historical main centres within Anglo-American literature, although some scholars point out London's influence is decreasing in favour of New York (Brouillette, 2007, 58). Indirectly, though, Gabilondo points out that China has become the centre of worldwide art sales, recently replacing NYC. However, he stresses that this does not mean that China is the actual centre of the WLF: "Still, Chinese literature, cinema and music have failed to make significant inroads into this multipolar power (except the martial-art films of Hong Kong)" (46). So, we can conclude that for Gabilondo, NYC is still the symbolic centre of the WLF, with China threatening this hegemony.

Commented [I12]: Added. New reference within World Literature's field

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Another issue linked to this is how a literary work attached to a dominated (*dominé*) literature can achieve –in Casanova's terms– *littérisation*, or in other words, what is the dialectics between dominated and dominant literature fields like. Gabilondo gives some clues in relation to Basque literature by criticizing some aspects of Casanova's theory, in particular, her dichotomy between nationalist and modernist literature. Gabilondo (2012, 2013) proposes a more complex system in which a so-called nationalist writer (Saizarbitoria, Sarrionandia) can achieve much more literary autonomy than a so-called modernist one (Atxaga, Uribe) who seeks international success and follows global neoliberal rules. In this sense, the image Uribe gives of the NYC (Sarasola, 2016) concurs with this desire for internationalization described by Gabilondo, although the literary critic alludes to this dependency only with respect to Madrid.

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4- Conclusions

The BLF is in a relevant situation when the forces in the WLF are analysed. Situated geographically between France and Spain and, therefore, between two of the most powerful fields of literature, and under the ongoing influence, in the current globalized world, of the

Field of Literature of the United States, the BLF is subject to fast power changes. Although the BLF has developed considerably within only a few decades and is now a relatively consistent literary field in southern Europe, Madrid and New York are still the two capitals that are symbolically dominating it. Specially Madrid, as has been already pointed out, among others, by Apalategi, Egaña, Gabilondo. Nevertheless, at the same time, we can see a ongoing tendency to seek legitimization power in New York.

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We can establish three periods in modern Basque literature in which it has been dominated by three different capitals.

Firstly, it was in the 1970s and 1980s that the BLF was instituted as such, in other words, when Basque literature acquired (semi)autonomy and set up an economic and cultural system. This was the era that saw the setting up of the autonomous Basque institutions, the UPV/EHU-University of the Basque Country, the main publishing houses, many literary journals etc. In this context, Donostia-San Sebastian was the main capital of the field, because the most important literary agents were located there or around there.

At the beginning of the 1990s, while the power of the BLF was increasing, another capital, this time a foreign one, appeared as the most influential capital for Basque literature. Symbolically, coinciding with the Spanish National Award that Atxaga's *Obabakoak* received in 1989, Madrid became the capital of the BLF. In order to gain literary recognition, a Basque writer needed to be translated into Spanish (by a Spanish publishing house) and be recognized in Madrid (via awards etc.). Many Basque writers were, therefore, looking towards Madrid, as Saizarbitoria's complaint about the lack of time to translate in the time between the Durango Fair and the submission deadline for the Spanish National Award shows. This dependency was confirmed in a way in 2002 when Elorriaga's *SPrako tranbia* won the same award, and he, who had not had anything published before, became quickly

endorsed with his *opera prima*. Something similar happened with Uribe and *Bilbao-New York-Bilbao*.

Nevertheless, parallel to this process, the symbolic power of Madrid, and of the Spanish National Award, in particular, seemed to be suffering fatigue. Partly due to the context of the social and cultural crisis in Spain and the loss of the legitimization power of the award, some Basque writers have tried to seek endorsement by other means. This is especially clear in the new generations, in Cano and Uribe, the only two professional writers of their generation^{xxv}. Both have shown, each in a different way, an inclination towards New York and have portrayed the city as the place to go for a writer or an artist. New York is for Uribe the place where one can get definitive literary or artistic endorsement, the place to recite your writings (Bowery Poetry Club) and to go to literary events and dinners. This is not, however, unique to the writers of the new generation. Even a writer who has been consecrated internationally via Madrid like Atxaga has become linked to New York recently. The Atxaga Chair at the University of New York can be regarded as the latest major effort of the BLF to get endorsement in New York. All this shows that the SLF is not sufficient in order to get international recognition and enter the World Republic of Letters.

Following this argument, we could ask whether this might be seen as a part of a bigger process in which the power relations in the WLF have changed in the last few decades. The BLF, as a relatively small emergent literary field, can show us some tendencies of these types of fields that point to the capitals where they are seeking endorsement. In this sense, it seems appropriate to point out that the BLF has not manifested any interest in Paris in order to get international literary recognition, even when part of the BLF is located in the French State. In that respect it is important to note that some important Basque writers from the Continental Basque Country that are translated into French and/or write as well in French, have been endorsed in the Peninsular Basque Country, that is to say, in the part that is within

the Spanish State. All this suggest to us that in a multipolar globalized WLF, Paris is no longer the capital of the World Republic of Letters, and that New York has nowadays a much more power of endorsement.

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i
i Hereinafter the BLF.

ii

ii Hereinafter the WLF.

iii

iii We prefer to speak about semi-autonomy rather than autonomy following Hal Foster's (2011) characterization of aesthetic autonomy.

^{iv} The concept of "influence" used in the article is understood in mere systemic terms, that is radically different from the stylistic meaning more commonly used in literary studies. By the term influence we refer to the legitimization power of a certain literary field and, consequently, its power to attract other fields to its dynamics and structures.

v

v In geographical terms, the BLF borders on the French Literary Field to the North and the Spanish Literary Field to the South. Moreover, there is a space in the BLF linked to the English Literary Field, consisting of the literature of the American diaspora, such as Robert Laxalt's works.

^{vi} Atxaga has been "thoroughly recognized for having internationalized Basque literature" (González-Allende & Ascunce, 2018). He has received several international literary prizes: Grinzane Cavour, Mondello, Cesare Pavese, Spanish National Prize.

vii

vii Hereinafter the SLF.

viii

viii Maybe, the most important exception was Koldo Mitxelena and the journal *Egan*.

ix

ix This is definitely a rarity bearing in mind that a part of the Basque Country (Iparralde or the Continental Basque Country) is located within the French State, and that many important Basque writers come from there. In any case, the issue is that Paris has no influence on the BLF, particularly when compared with Madrid's influence.

x

x Andima Ibiñagabeitia, for example, one of Mirande's closest friends and the man who introduced Peillen to him, was living in Caracas at that time.

xi

xi Milles Pages Prize, Atlantic Pyrenees Three Crowns Prize and shortlisted for the European Literary Prize.

xii

xii A State policy formulated in 2012 and which aims to promote Spain abroad.

xiii

xiii Years before there had been other refusal: Els Joglars company in 1994 (in Theatre), and Daniel Gil in 2001 (in Design)

xiv

xiv *Obabakoak* received it in 1989.

xv

xv They did not receive any awards at all.

xvi

xvi It received the Spanish Critics' Award, but this award is actually given by only one or two critics (Jon Kortazar and/or Javier Rojo) opinion.

^{xvii} This tendency could be identified even within SLF, especially in new generations authors that are being endorsed by New York. One of these examples is Gonzalo Torné, a Catalan writer writing in Spanish that can be situated within the North American modernist literary tradition. His work has been translated into English and reviewed and praised in the New York Times. More clearly, Zadie Smith is a good example of an author that the international success is linked to her arrival to New York and the development of her literary career there.

xviii

xviii *Kilkerren hotsak* (Edorta Jimenez), *Koaderno gorria* (Arantxa Urretabizkaia), *Rock'n Roll* (Aingeru Epaltza), *Hamaseigarrenean aidanez* (Anjel Lertxundi), *Pasaia blues* (Harkaitz Cano), *Amaren eskuak* (Karmele Jaio) and *Zulo bat uretan* (Iñigo Aranbarri), all translated directly from Basque.

xix

xix The short story anthology *Emekiro*, *Sisifo maiteminez* (Laura Mintegi), *Norbait dabil sute eskaileran* (Harkaitz Cano), and *Han goitik itsasoa ikusten da* (Julen Gabiria), all translated directly from Basque.

xx

xx The main works have been published by Harvill Secker, and translated by Margaret Jull.

xxi

xxi *Nerea eta biok*.

^{xxii} *Bilbao-New York-Bilbao* is an autofictional novel.

xxiii

xxiii The institute whose aim is to promote Basque culture all over the world.

xxiv

xxiv The Etxepare Basque Institute is a public institute that reports to the Basque Autonomous Community Government.